

ANTIARTHRITIC POTENTIAL OF GYMNEMA SYLVESTRE ETHANOLIC EXTRACT VIA DOWNREGULATION OF INFLAMMATORY CYTOKINES IN RAT MODEL

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Abstract

In this research work, we examined the anti-arthritis effects of *G. sylvestre* leaf extract on an arthritic model caused by Freund Complete Adjuvant (FCA). The bioactive components of *G. sylvestre* leaf, flavonoids and phenols, had a pain-relieving effect by inhibiting the cyclo-oxygenase enzyme and protecting the joint from damage. Thirty rats were split into five groups at random: the first group received normal diet, the second group was arthritic control (FCA injection), the third group had standard control (methotrexate), and the fourth and fifth groups received low and high dosages of the drug for 21 days. On the 29th day, blood samples were taken. Qualitative and quantitative phytochemical analysis, Paw thickness, body weight index, liver and kidney function, pro-inflammatory indicators, oxidative stress markers and histopathology were among the many parameters that were examined. SOD, and catalase were markedly elevated in the treated groups, whereas creatinine, urea, AST, ALT, TNF- α , IL-6 and RF levels were decreased. Ankle joint histology revealed less bone degradation and mononuclear cell infiltration. Therefore, it concluded that *G. sylvestre* leaf extract has antioxidant and anti-inflammatory qualities. The data was analyzed using both one-way and two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA).

INTRODUCTION

An immunologically inflammatory, systemic condition is rheumatoid arthritis (RA) that is linked to a decreased lifespan of 8–15 years and usually affects people who have serious health issues. It is believed that oxidative stress plays a part in the onset of RA. A systemic autoimmune disease, rheumatoid arthritis results in joint breaks, stiffness, edema, and puffiness. About

1% of people worldwide are afflicted by it, and its prevalence rises with age and is higher in women. Although the precise etiology is yet unknown, genetics and environmental factors interact to cause it (Finckh et al., 2022).

The synovium, the membrane that surrounds joints and secretes synovial fluid for cushioning and lubrication, is the site of rheumatoid

arthritis (RA). This fluid provides oxygen and nutrition to the cartilage, that is mainly composed of collagen and maintains joints. Extended inflammation of the synovium in RA is caused by abnormal immune responses that result in the production of damage-causing chemicals. Collagen breakdown results in joint space constriction and bone deterioration. The growth of pannus, a group of fluids and immune cell types in the synovium that generates enzymes that degrade cartilage, aggravates damage (Karpiński et al., 2025).

NSAIDs, corticosteroids, and disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs) are all included in rheumatoid arthritis treatment regimens. Opioids and paracetamol are examples of NSAIDs that are used to alleviate RA pain by blocking cyclooxygenase enzymatic activity. Additionally, anti-TNF and IL-6 antibodies are used to treat RA (Magni et al., 2021). Although glucocorticoids have strong anti-inflammatory properties, long-term usage of these drugs can have negative side effects include glaucoma and muscle and skin atrophy (Niculet et al., 2020).

Herbal remedies are thought to be a viable substitute for synthetic medications with anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic properties that have fewer side effects. As a result, they serve as resources for the identification of molecules with these properties. Plants that contain salicylate have been used medicinally for many years, which led to the creation of aspirin, a common anti-inflammatory drug that is used extensively in contemporary medicine.

Traditional treatments for inflammatory diseases like hay fever, pain, headaches, and arthritis have included natural compounds having anti-inflammatory properties (Aslam et al., 2024).

A member of the Apocynaceae family, *Gymnema sylvestre* is a medicinal plant that grows in Australia, Asia, and Africa. It has long been

used as an anti-diabetic plant and is also used to treat bacterial infections, inflammation, indigestion, constipation, and asthma. Its main chemical components, gymnemic acids,

flavonoids, and alkaloids, are abundant in its leaves (Ibrahim, 2024). In this work, rats with FCA-induced arthritis were used to test the anti-arthritic effects of *Gymnema sylvestre* leaf ethanolic extract.

Materials and Methods

Extraction of the plant

Gymnema sylvestre leaves were purchased from a herbal store in Faisalabad. The specimen was cleaned using tap water first, followed by distilled water to remove any remaining dirt particles. The sample was first cut into little pieces and then allowed to dry for 15 days in the shade. The samples were then ground into a powder using a mechanical grinder. Following that, 70% ethanol was used to extract *G. sylvestre*. Every extraction procedure was performed three times. Following that, the extract was filtered, and the filtrate was gathered. The extract's solvent was evaporated in a hot water bath set at 60°C and then dried in hot air oven (Rahman et al., 2014).

Qualitative phytochemical analysis

With a few minor adjustments, Subhan's phytochemical analysis method was applied to the plant extract to identify the presence of various bioactive primary and secondary phytochemicals such as alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, glycosides, tannins and saponins (Subhan et al., 2021).

DPPH assay of *Gymnema sylvestre*

A previously published technique was used, with a small modification, to measure the DPPH radical scavenging activity (Aslam et al., 2024). The results of several plant extract concentrations were used to determine the plant's IC50.

Total flavonoids and total phenolic contents

With few modifications, the Sajid method was used to calculate the total flavonoids and total phenolic compounds. Plant extract, distilled water, NaOH (4%, 5%), and AlCl₃ (10%) were applied to a microplate for the measurement of total flavonoids, and the absorbance at 510 nm was noted. The TFC result was expressed in

milligrams of catechin equivalent per 100 grams of the sample. To measure total phenolic components, fill the microplate with 0.8 ml of normal water, 0.05 ml of plant extract, and 0.05 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. Add 0.1 ml of Na₂Co₃ after 3 minutes. Measure the absorbance at 725 nm after an hour at room temperature. The TPC information was expressed using gallic acid equivalent (Abbas et al., 2025; Sajid et al., 2025).

Experimental Protocol

For this study, thirty rats were divided into five groups at random. G1, the normal control (NC), was given the proper food and water for the duration of the 28-day experiment. G2 was an arthritic control group that was given a normal diet following a single FCA injection to induce arthritis. G3 was the standard group (SG), and they received 0.5 mg/kg PO of methotrexate. For 21 days, treatment groups G4 and G5 were given ethanolic extract of *Gymnema sylvestre* at low doses (250 mg/kg) and high doses (500 mg/kg).

Induction of Arthritis

Rats were given 0.075 ml of FCA into the sub-plantar area of their left hind paw to cause arthritis (Arora et al., 2015).

Physical Parameters

Body weight and paw thickness

Each rat's weight and paw thickness were measured on days 0, 7, 14, 21, and 28 using a weighing scale and a vernier caliper, respectively,

in order to evaluate the effects of medications on physical parameters.

Serum collection

Centrifuging tubes free of EDTA for ten minutes at 4500 rpm was used to collect serum. The serum was then separated into labeled Eppendorf tubes and stored at -20°C for use in oxidative stress assessments, biological testing, and the detection of inflammatory mediators.

Determination of health markers

The levels of liver functioning biomarkers like ALT and AST as well as kidney function biomarkers like urea and creatinine were assessed in the serum using the appropriate calorimetric kits.

Estimation of oxidative stress and inflammatory markers

Calorimetric kits and ELISA kits were utilized to estimate antioxidant defense markers such as catalase (CAT) and superoxide dismutase (SOD), and inflammatory markers like TNF-α and IL-6.

Histopathological examination

The liver and ankle underwent histological examination. Hematoxylin and eosin stain (H&E) was used to stain the samples after they had been fixed in a 10% formalin solution.

Statistical analysis

CRD was used in the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to analyze the data. Tukey's test at the 5% level of significance (P ≤ 0.05) was used for repeated comparison of the data.

Results

Qualitative phytochemical analysis

Table 1. The table displays the findings of the qualitative phytochemical study. Present (+), absent (-).

Phytochemical	Result
Alkaloids	+
Flavonoids	+
Phenols	+
Glycosides	+
Tannins	-
Saponins	+

Quantitative phytochemical analysis

With an IC50 of 19.06 µg/mL, the results show that *Gymnema sylvestre* exhibited antioxidant activity (DPPH) in comparison to the standard control, ascorbic acid (IC50 = 5.94 µg/mL). The

current study's findings showed that the aqueous extract of *Gymnema sylvestre* had the highest concentrations of flavonoid (2.61 ± 0.01 mg/g QE) and phenolic (21.44 ± 0.7 mg/g GAE) contents.

Figure 1. DPPH assay of *Gymnema sylvestre* leaf extract

Physical parameters

Every experimental animal's body weight was recorded on days 0, 7, 14, 21, and 28 of the trial. Following the induction of arthritis, the normal and treatment groups showed a substantial rise in body weight (p < 0.05), while the arthritic group showed a significant increase (p < 0.05), a steady rise in body weight was noted in the therapy

groups. On the seventh day following the onset of arthritis, the paw thickness was considerably (p<0.05) greater in the arthritic control group. Paw thickness began to decrease significantly (p< 0.05) following treatment with low and high doses of *G. sylvestre* leaf extract. Paw thickness was significantly reduced in the treated groups.

Figure 2. Effect of *Gymnema sylvestre* leaf extract on (A) body weight and (B) paw thickness

Health markers
A statistical analysis of serum AST, ALT, Creatinine and Urea revealed a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in the arthritic group relative to the

normal control group. Following treatment with low and high doses of *G. sylvestre* leaf extract, the AST, ALT, Creatinine and Urea levels were dramatically decreased ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 3. Effect of *Gymnema sylvestre* leaf extract on Health markers. (A); AST level, (B); ALT level, (C); Creatinine and (D); Urea level. * Represents a significant difference of normal group with all other groups, # and α shows the significance of the arthritic and standard groups from other groups respectively.

Estimation of oxidative stress

There was a significant ($p < 0.05$) correlation between the normal group and every other group, according to statistical analysis. The arthritic and treated groups showed a strong correlation. a

significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between the treated and arthritic groups. The catalase and SOD levels were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher in the treated groups than in the arthritic group.

Figure 4. Effect of *Gymnema sylvestre* leaf extract on oxidative stress markers. (A); SOD level, (B); Catalase level. * Represents a significant difference of normal group with all other groups, # and α shows the significance of the arthritic and standard groups from other groups, respectively.

Inflammatory cytokines

A statistical analysis of serum TNF-α, IL-6 and Rf levels revealed a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in the arthritic group relative to the normal control

group. Following treatment with low and high doses of *G. sylvestre* leaf extract, a significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease was observed in serum TNF-α, IL-6 and Rf levels.

Figure 5. Effect of *Gymnema sylvestre* leaf extract on inflammatory cytokines. (A); TNF- level, (B); IL-6 level and (C); Rf level. * Represents a significant difference of normal group with all other groups, # and α shows the significance of the arthritic and standard groups from other groups, respectively.

Histopathology

When compared to normal rats, the histopathology of the ankle joint in arthritic control rats revealed a significant infiltration of mononuclear cells, bone degradation, and pannus development. Compared to arthritic control, inflammatory cell infiltration, bone degradation, and pannus development were extract treated groups.

significantly reduced in treated rats with *G. sylvestre*. When comparing arthritic rats to normal control rats, histological analysis of the liver revealed hepatocellular damage in the form of significant vacuolization, nuclear congestion, and necrosis. However, there has been a notable improvement in *G. sylvestre* leaf

Figure 6. Effect of *Gymnema sylvestre* leaf extract on histopathology of ankle and liver. (A); ankle joint and (B); liver. a-e represents normal, arthritic, standard, low and high dose group of *Gymnema sylvestre* leaf extract, respectively.

Discussion

One percent of people worldwide suffer from rheumatoid arthritis, a painful and progressive inflammatory disease classified by immunological processes of the joints (Riaz et al., 2025). There is little information available regarding the prevalence of RA in Pakistan; nevertheless, Karachi has the highest point prevalence (Naqviet al., 2019). The current study demonstrated that leaf extract has anti-arthritic properties.

Herbal remedies are thought to be a viable substitute for synthetic medications with anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic properties that have fewer side effects. As a result, they serve as

resources for the identification of molecules with these properties (Banik et al., 2020). Their pharmacological characteristics are chiefly due to the presence of phytochemicals, which are mostly secondary metabolites of plants. Various impacts of pharmacology, such as anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, anti-hypertensive, anti-diabetic, and antioxidant, have been shown to be successfully regulated by these phytochemicals (Nwozo et al., 2023).

The qualitative phytochemical analysis of *G. sylvestre* leaf extract showed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, saponins and glycosides which are assumed to have anti-

inflammatory properties. Additionally, by squelching the free radicals in the DPPH experiment, the extract of *G. sylvestre* demonstrated antioxidant activity (IC₅₀ = 19.06 µg/mL), which may be attributed to the presence of phenols and flavonoid components. The current study's findings showed that the aqueous extract of *G. sylvestre* had the highest concentrations of flavonoid (2.61 ± 0.01 mg/g QE) and phenolic (21.44 ± 0.7 mg/g GAE) contents. Similar study was reported by Abhiram et al., (2023).

Because of inflammation, arthritis caused a marked increase in liver and kidney indicators. However, liver markers are thought to be more valuable in arthritis, and their elevated value suggests that free radicals mediated hepatic harm as well as impairment of organs and bones. In our research findings there was increased level of health markers such as AST, ALT, creatinine and urea. After treatment with *G. sylvestre* leaf extract health markers level was significantly improved as reported in a previous study (He et al., 2019).

In the pathophysiology of RA, these pro-inflammatory mediators are essential for articular manifestation, including increased inflammatory cell infiltration, especially of T cells, B lymphocytes, and macrophages, bone erosion that leads to the formation of autoantibodies, and the release of TNF-α and IL-6 (Singh et al., 2020). Our study results showed the higher level of TNF-α, IL-6 and Rf in arthritic group rat. Level of TNF-α, IL-6 and Rf was significantly decreased after treatment.

The impact of *G. sylvestre* leaf extract on liver, and ankle joint was determined by histopathological examination. The arthritic group displayed hyperplasia of the synovium, pannus development, bone loss, and mononuclear cells. The findings showed a decrease in bone deterioration and mononuclear cells. Additionally, liver histology revealed a considerable number of inflammatory cells, hepatic cell congestion, and necrosis, all of which were considerably lessened when arthritic rats were given *G. sylvestre* leaf extract. These results were in accordance with Hussain et al. (2021).

Author's Contribution

Ifraha Abbas, Muhammad Yahya and Sahar Javed designed the study; Ifraha abbas, Shagufta Malik, Musfira Shahid, Nabila Naheed and Samrah Nadeem analyzed the data and prepared the draft manuscript; Laiba Batool, Ajwa and Sahar Javed critically revised the paper.

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